

THE FUNCTION OF SENTENCE STRESS

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Abstract. *In this article you will get acquainted with the functions of sentence stress and how sentence stress can help you understand rapid spoken English and what it offers English its rhythm or "beat". Moreover, sentence stress is accent on sure phrases inside a sentence and functional words are not stressed.*

Keywords: *Stress, pronunciation, intonation, constitutive and distinctive features.*

ФУНКЦИЯ УДАРЕНИЯ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В этой статье вы познакомитесь с функциями ударения в предложении и тем, как ударение в предложении может помочь вам понять быстрый разговорный английский и что оно предлагает английскому языку в его ритме или «такте». Кроме того, ударение в предложении - это ударение на определенных фразах внутри предложения, а служебные слова не имеют ударения.*

Ключевые слова: *Ударение, произношение, интонация, конститутивные и отличительные признаки.*

Stress is a beneficial way of signaling what's vital within sentence. It gives the listener clues to hear to components of the sentence which are more important. If stress is not used, or used incorrectly, the listener may misinterpret the distinct meaning or have problem choosing out important concepts. In a sentence like " I will write you a referral now " you can pick out to spotlight distinct parts, relying on what you mean. Stress is used to signal things like new information, contrasting information and transition (changes of topic). Stress combines with intonation and phrasing to spotlight distinctive parts of a sentence.

Sentence stress in English is the way a speaker highlights satisfactory phrases in every sentence. It helps the listener focal aspect on fundamental components and recognize the speaker's meaning.

For example, The health practitioner will see you now. Some phrases will be larger prominent than others and one will be the most prominent. Stress is carried out the equal way in a sentence as it is in a phrase – in addition be by using making the pressured syllable longer, louder and distinct pitch. Sentence stress is the second most essential component of intonation. Its essential functions are to single out phrases in a sentence in accordance to their relative semantic importance and to supply and sufficient rhythmical structure of sentence. For ex: I am going library.

The given sentence is shaped by one sense –crew and one sentence stress which function together with speech melody determining the degree and function of stress in a sentence. Like semantic, grammatical and rhythmical elements which are in relationship to every different, although the semantic thing is more essential in English than the other elements. The presence of stress in any utterance proves it constitutive feature. H . Kurath distinguishes two sort of stress 1) Sentence-stress , which is accompanied by way of a pitch figure and alerts the stop of a segment of discourse 2) phrase stress used at or shut to the give up of English phrases, irrespective of their syntactic structure.

Learning difficulties of Sentence Stress

You cannot choose the place to region the stress in men or women's words, however, you can pick the place to location the stress in a sentence. It depends on what you're attempting to highlight. Stressing an exclusive phrase can exchange the meaning. Common issues include stressing too many phrases in a sentence, not stressing any phrase clearly, knowing which phrases to stress relies upon on the meaning, context and what you and your listener already knows (shared knowledge). If you can hear stress in the speech of the people you are talking with you will be able to select up what they suppose is vital too.

To sum up, English intonation is difficult for learner. Improving the ability to hear, understanding and reproductive sentence stress are necessary requirement to grasp English Intonation. In addition, do not forget main rules sentence stress as they are 1) Content words are stressed 2) Structure words are unstressed 3) The time between stressed word is always the same. It would be impossible to apprehend any language except following a positive pattern of stress because languages rely on the stress, rhythm and intonation to be determined and these are the major challenges of any languages different than the native one.

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